

DESTINATION EARTH CO-DESIGN TOOLKIT

Introduction and overview of the co-design methodology

December 2025

Funded by
the European Union

Destination Earth

implemented by

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In many sectors, co-design stands at the cornerstone of product and service development, enabling designers to engage with users and understand their specific needs. But in the context of data-based service development, co-designing seems particularly challenging: users are often not clearly identified, and their understanding of the potential of modelling and geospatial data is limited. Moreover, service providers must navigate the complexities of integrating diverse data types, advanced analytical tools, and application environments. To address these challenges, and support the uptake of DestinE, a robust methodological framework is essential to unlock the full potential of the platform.

The Destination Earth initiative is a comprehensive effort aiming to develop a high-precision digital twin of the Earth. The DestinE Platform integrates several dimensions: interfaces to a DestinE data lake and to a configurable set of data providers, hosting environments equipped with an ecosystem of advanced tools, applications or services.

This Co-design Toolkit is designed to support the future DestinE service providers in creating impactful services by leveraging these integrated resources through the DestinE Platform. The toolkit is built on cutting-edge methods and tools developed from:

- Extensive expertise in innovation management and design theory, largely demonstrated for the downstream EO sector in the framework of the H2020 e-shape project (Barbier et al., 2022).
- A comprehensive understanding of the technical and organizational challenges faced by Earth Observation and climate stakeholders.
- User validation through a series of pilot applications developed with the city of Marseille in support of the implementation of the 2030 low-carbon strategy, part of the EU Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. It delivered DestinE-based proofs of concepts addressing specific policy objectives actions co-designed in complex environments engaging a large diversity of actors.

This document introduces the Co-design Toolkit as the primary entry point for understanding and applying co-design methods in the context of DestinE. While the toolkit is particularly useful for service providers, it could be adaptable and relevant to a larger range of stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and data providers. Readers are encouraged to consider how the co-design methods may resonate with their specific perspectives and use cases, and feedback is welcome to refine and expand its applicability.

The structure of this introductory document is as follows: 1) A brief introduction to the co-design methods for DestinE 2) A detailed presentation of the proposed co-design methodology and the accompanying toolkit

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1. Introduction to the DestinE co-design toolkit

As the bridge between users and the DestinE components, the DestinE Platform plays a crucial role in providing the necessary access and processes that enable users to leverage data in ways that drive societal impact, aligned with European priorities.

The co-design methodology focuses on engaging user communities and fostering resilient, collaborative relationships with them. Its aim is to facilitate the identification of actionable solutions that address specific needs while supporting long-term sustainability and adaptability. This toolkit is designed to offer a co-design methodology that is specifically tailored to navigate the complexities of fragmented multi-stakeholder ecosystems, where interactions are often intricate and, at times, difficult to set up in a sustainable way.

As such, these methods and the toolkit presented in this document should be used by service providers and/or service developers to design new services.

1.1. Defining co-design

Co-design is an approach to design attempting to actively involve all stakeholders (e.g. service providers, customers, citizens, consumers, platforms...) in the design process to help ensure the results meets their specific needs and are usable. This approach shifts users from being mere recipients to active partners in the design process.

However, existing co-design methods and practices involve users through simple consultation and gathering their needs through a few questions or interviews at the start or end of a project. These methods reduce the user to a passive voice with limited design inputs, limiting the reach of user engagement and service adoption at the end of the design process.

On the contrary the co-design methodology proposed in this toolkit focuses on building resilient relationships between service providers and their users by involving users all along the co-design process. Co-design can thus be defined as :

«A form of collaborative innovation that puts a specific emphasis on the need of (re)inventing the relationships between the involved actors.» (Barbier, 2023)

This approach to co-design encompasses three critical aspects (figure 1):

- 1. A design aspect:** Co-design is directed towards the exploration of innovative solutions as to design services that suits users' needs at best.
- 2. A collective aspect:** Co-design relies on involving a heterogeneous set of actors that must collaborate to design the service
- 3. A crisis aspect:** Co-design should support the structuring of effective interaction patterns in situations where collaboration seems unlikely because the stakeholders involved know little about each other, are not used to working together and may have divergent interests.

The co-design methodology proposed through this toolkit should enable DestinE service providers to collaborate with a variety of users, some of them being even unknown, to co-design new services contributing to societal challenges in many areas e.g. climate, environment, risk reduction.

Figure 1. The three dimensions of co-design

1.2. Problem statement

Co-design methods stand as a consistent way to answer some of the key challenges faced by DestinE service providers, as synthesized in the figure 2 and discussed below.

1.2.1. Bridging grand distance¹ to reach users

Connecting DestinE with potential users can be challenging, as it requires bridging stakeholders from diverse sectors who may have little in common and might not even be aware of each other's existence. In other words, the stakeholders are separated by a form of “**grand distance**”, where they appear as largely unknown to each other.

Overall, in the field of earth system science and data, the issue of grand distance unfolds in a particularly extreme way (Barbier, 2023). Numerous stakeholders could benefit from these data and models. However, many potential users are unaware not only of how to leverage these resources, but even that such data might bring value to their activities. At the same time, the experts who master these data may not fully grasp the sector-specific needs or challenges that could be addressed through earth system data.

Under these conditions, collective action seems far from guaranteed. Indeed this grand distance creates multiple challenges across various dimensions for the stakeholders:

- **Cognitive:** Stakeholders may have different understandings of the challenges they face, requiring the creation of a shared understanding.
- **Technical:** They may possess varying levels of expertise, which can hinder their ability to communicate efficiently or design effectively together.
- **Organizational:** They must navigate the boundaries of their respective organizations and adapt to new processes and ways of working.

¹ “grand distance”: a situation where actors have no obvious way to interact since they show a high degree of distance on many dimensions e.g. cognitive, organizational, geographical, institutional, social.

Figure 2. Some of the key challenges addressed by co-design

In the context of initiatives such as DestinE, these challenges even unfold at a deeper, systemic level since a key objective is to connect industry to long term sustainable applications that answer a concrete user demand. Beyond raising awareness about the potential of data, the central issue thus lies in bridging those with the technical capacity, such as service providers who understand the long-term potential of the data, with actors capable of generating value from it as to align the services provided with the very user demand. Therefore, the focus enlarges from educating users about data to supporting intermediaries who can identify latent demands and markets, create meaningful services, and build bridges to user communities, effectively transforming raw data into applied, sustainable impact.

The proposed co-design methodology supports a collective exploration by the service providers, their potential users, and other relevant stakeholders, fostering mutual learning and shared understanding.

An adaptable toolkit to be used by a variety of stakeholders

While this document currently reflects the perspective of service providers, the ambition of the methodology and toolkit is to be adaptable and usable by a wider range of actors, including end users such as public authorities. As the toolkit evolves, the goal is to make it a resource that can support diverse stakeholders in engaging with and applying earth system data. The co-design team actively welcomes diverse perspectives to refine and expand the toolkit’s relevance across different contexts, with further customization to be explored in subsequent iterations.

1.2.2. Multilaterality – putting complex chains of actors into motion

Developing services based on data requires a complex chain of stakeholders with diverse skills and interests to be set in motion.

This effort could be schematically described as connecting various and highly heterogeneous socio-economic ecosystems: the ecosystem of data science at large, with the various ecosystems of potential usages, that do not share the same dynamics, time horizons (e.g. very

long cycles to develop new measuring instruments compared to short timeline of actions in the data usage context), performance logics and competencies.

Co design specifically aims at connecting these various and heterogeneous ecosystems of data and usages, through multi-stakeholder mobilization and engagement. The proposed co-design method relies on disentangling the various needs to identify the right sequence of interactions within the chain of stakeholders.

DestinE's ecosystem is complex: in addition to having a grand distance between a service provider and the end user, we observe a multiplicity of stakeholders engaged in complex structure. These additional stakeholders include the platform provider (ESA or DestinE entrusted entities), service providers (e.g., Mines Paris PSL O.I.E.), and end users (e.g., cities), each filling distinct roles in the data journey.

Acknowledging this stakeholder diversity and positioning, various potential co-design interactions emerge, necessitating careful structuring to optimize usefulness, usability, and operability of the potential service. This highlights the necessity of a precise diagnosis of co-design needs, a task central to the user monitoring framework's purpose.

1.2.3. Scalability - Managing contextualization and genericity

As an emergent platform, DestinE aims to support the development and dissemination of that go beyond a single use case or user, demonstrating broad relevance and strong potential for scalability across diverse contexts. This ambition serves as a cornerstone for promoting extensive dissemination and use of DestinE services, while rationalizing investments and efforts in service development and diffusion by supporting economies of scale.

For service providers, it implies to closely manage the tension between two potentially competing objectives in service design:

1. Providing features that are context-specific enough to meet the precise needs of particular user groups and integrate seamlessly into their workflows and practices.
2. Defining generic technical building blocks that could be subsequently reused and adapted to meet similar needs across different user communities.

In other words, it implies finding the right balance between contextualization and genericity to ensure that services are both tailored and reusable across multiple use cases.

Throughout the co-design process, various mechanisms can be enacted to reconcile the need for contextual solutions with the degree of necessary for service reuse. The co-design toolkit offers practical tools and best practices to support these mechanisms.

1.3. Key objectives and principles

As a methodology for user-driven development of data-intensive services, co-design relies on essential objectives and key principles that service providers should keep in mind.

1.3.1. Key principles from the perspective of the relationship between actors

Since the co-design methodology is inherently oriented towards collaborative innovation, some fundamental principles apply to the relationship between the stakeholders engaged in the process:

Co-design principle #1 - Users' needs as a critical starting point

The co-design methodology starts from the concrete needs of end users. It therefore acknowledges that technological solutions are only as valuable as their alignment with real-world problems and user contexts. Such user-centric approach prioritizes a deep understanding of the users' activities, the challenges they face, and the specific goals they aim to achieve.

Equally important is recognizing users' competencies, constraints, and contexts of use to ensure that the services are not only functional but also usable and impactful.

Achieving this depth of user knowledge is possible through close, iterative interactions, where mutual learning occurs, and users actively shape the solutions to meet their needs effectively.

Co-design principle #2 - 'Designing the co-' as an imperative

An effective co-design approach implies to acknowledge from the start that the co-design actions should not only focus on the design of the service, but also on the design of the relationships, i.e. it has to design the 'co'. In this respect, the outcomes of interactions should include agreements for future cooperation between participants.

Co-design principle #3 - Resilient-fit as a key goal

The co-design actions should aim to establish a 'resilient fit' between participants, rather than a 'quick fit'.

- 'Quick-fit' actions would focus on finding one type of interaction between data and usages ecosystems (single list of requirements with one user, in a punctual relationship). This is the most current pathway in developing "proof-of-concepts".
- Instead, 'resilient-fit' actions aim at generating a range of alternatives (regarding the lists of requirements, the stakeholders involved, the types of partnerships), providing a methodological framework particularly adapted to changing environments.

This point is critical to foster service resilience and sustainability, as service providers will have to deal with constant evolutions of both the data field and the different usage fields. In this perspective, the co-design process builds-up a series of interactions designed to progressively shape and consolidate 'building blocks' of the long-term development of the service's strategy, intertwined with the evolution of both data and usage fields.

1.3.2. Key principles from the perspective of service development

For service providers, co-design goes beyond solving technical issues; it addresses the question of value creation for the end-user. As such, a sustainable service operated on DestinE is not only a service that works (**operability**). It should also create value to the users (**usefulness**), empower them by becoming part of their daily practices, processes and tools (**usability**), and remain relevant, maintained and valuable on the long run (**sustainability**). Ultimately, the service should also be relevant in a variety of contexts (**scalability**).

Therefore, from a technical standpoint, ensuring the usefulness, operability, usability, sustainability, and scalability of services constitutes the five primary objectives guiding the co-design of any service (Figure 3):

- **Defining the scope of usefulness** requires identifying consistent potential users and the specific problems the services can help them address. This typically requires close, repeated interactions with users.

- **Ensuring Operability on the DestinE platform** requires aligning the service design with the platform’s resources, data, and protocols, ensuring that services can run on it and/or be built upon it. This typically involves establishing a co-design relationship with the platform team.
- **Fostering services usability** requires clarifying the processes and tools impacted by the service, to ensure that the service will be usable and adopted by users. This involves a fine-grained understanding of users’ operations and workflows.
- **Promoting services sustainability** requires involving users as long-term partners, potentially through contractual relationships, and ensuring that services remain viable, updated, and accessible over time, taking into account technical, intellectual property, and cost considerations.
- **Supporting service scalability** requires providing options for use in different contexts, with various stakeholders, and even for alternative purposes. This typically involves assessing the degree of genericity of the need to be addressed, eventually by engaging with others potential users.

Figure 3. Usefulness, Operability, Usability, Sustainability and Scalability as the five critical imperatives for service development

2. How to use the co-design toolkit

The co-design journey can be broken down into four essential phases, each crucial for ensuring the successful development of services, as illustrated in Figure 4. To effectively navigate the unique challenges that arise in each phase, the co-design toolkit equips service providers with a comprehensive set of tools, methods, and best practices. In the following sections, we provide a concise overview of these four key phases. For more in-depth information on the specific tools, templates, and methodologies that support this process, please refer to Section 3.

Figure 4. The four key steps of the co-design journey

Critical insights

It may be tempting to assume that the co-design workshops are the only essential part of the co-design journey; however, this is a misconception that can lead to major mistakes, ultimately undermining the entire co-design process. In fact, all phases are equally vital, with particular emphasis on the diagnosis and outcome stages, which are crucial for ensuring a comprehensive and successful design approach.

2.1. Phase 1 - Approaching users **Essential Worksheet 1**

The first step of the co-design journey relies on identifying and engaging with potential users, which requires specific efforts. It should be understood as a progressive process focused on staging a fertile ground for interactions and collaborative work. Its key goals are to establish visibility and trust, while simultaneously gaining insights from the perspective of potential users, creating a foundation for collaborative working relationships.

The overall process for approaching users can be broken down into four main steps that support a progressive path from the coarse understanding of complex use ecosystems towards the initialization of co-design relationships with engaged users. These steps and associated actions are documented in the essential worksheet 1 as follows:

1. The preliminary diagnosis (step 1) focuses on a first exploration of the potential use ecosystem based on data collection from secondary sources (public reports, etc.).
2. The identification of potential users (step 2) focuses on targeting a set of promising potential users based on the analysis of the information collected during the preliminary diagnosis.
3. The user approach (step 3) focuses on establishing first contacts with targeted users to assess their interest. It may rely on preliminary interactions by email, phone call and other communication methods.
4. The user engagement (step 4) focuses on establishing closer interactions with targeted users to engage them within the co-design process. It typically relies on preliminary meetings focused on building the foundations for the co-design streams to be launched.

While this entire process allows to engage with unknown users, any service providers can begin their journey at different stages if potential users have already been identified, approached or even engaged.

Regardless, beyond documenting the different steps of this process, the co-design toolkit offers tools to support the journey towards user engagement, through a dedicated User Monitoring Framework documented in the essential worksheet 1.

This framework focuses on establishing a fine-grained understanding of potential users to support the emergence of promising relationships and to facilitate the initiation and execution of joint co-design activities.

At this stage, this framework is intended to be used by service providers for engaging in co-design activities with potential end-users during the initial stages of service design. However, as stated earlier, the goal is for it to evolve into a resource that can be used by a broader range of stakeholders.

2.2. Phase 2 - Co-design diagnosis **Essential Worksheet 2**

The co-design diagnosis is critical to assess the co-design needs through an exploratory approach. This step, which must be completed before any workshops with identified users, should clearly assess the technical system (Digital infrastructure, Data, Information, Usage, Value-Embedding Usage, and Users' Needs) and the relationships between the actors, which plays a critical role in shaping the overall success of the co-design journey.

It helps identify missing elements and key challenges, with the goal of structuring a consistent co-design action plan. While workshops — organized based on a thorough diagnosis— will follow, the diagnosis is an independent and foundational step that must be continuously nourished and refined, especially after establishing initial contacts, and throughout the co-design process.

The co-design diagnosis should be performed to assess:

- 1) The technical system and its missing elements

- 2) The processes and competencies required to complete the technical system
- 3) The actors and their interactions

To perform an effective diagnosis on each of these dimensions, the diagnosis of each co-design initiative relies on the representation of the service on a ‘data-information-value’ framework introduced in the Worksheet 2. It represents the ‘data journey’ from raw data to information, up to usages, the actors involved in the different transformation processes and the competencies required.

2.3. Phase 3 – Co-design workshops **Essential Worksheet 3**

The third phase of the co-design methodology involves organizing a series of co-design workshops. The primary objective of these workshops is to foster collaboration between service providers and users, ensuring that user needs are at the heart of the solution. Workshops can focus on clarifying user needs, but they can also serve a variety of other purposes, such as building working relationships with potential partners, addressing integration issues with infrastructure providers, or exploring new uses for existing services, for instance.

Given the diverse range of purposes and action strategies that may be required during this phase, five key considerations are critical when organizing co-design activities:

- 1) The co-design workshops must be structured as to move forward gradually in resolving the issues identified by the diagnosis phase: not all problems will be solved at the same time in a single workshop. The diagnosis phase should serve as a guide to structure the sequence of co-design workshops.
- 2) Since each workshop should be focused on a specific problem identified during the diagnosis, the protocols followed during these workshops should be adapted to these specific problems. Typically, this action phase can be built on as many different protocols as there are workshops. However, whatever the protocol to be built, three critical aspects of any workshop should be considered and adapted during the preparation of any workshop:
 - A carefully crafted agenda is essential to facilitate constructive dialogue and ensure that the specific objectives of the workshop are met.
 - Close interactions with participants should be organized to guide users in articulating their needs effectively. This requires thoughtful preparation in advance to ensure that the environment fosters openness and comfort. For instance, facilitators can pre-define participant subgroups based on shared characteristics or interests to encourage compatibility and enhance collaboration.
 - Well-prepared templates are necessary to provide a clear, common, and unambiguous framework that supports productive dialogue and interaction throughout the session.

Independent from the structure of co-design workshops and the specific protocols used, three key insights must be kept in mind:

- **‘Designing the co-’ is at the very heart of co-design workshops.** This recommendation emphasizes the collaborative aspect of the co-design process, where multiple stakeholders actively engage in shaping relationships and solutions together. At its core, this approach involves progressively building up localized collectives that gather pinpointed actors within the considered ecosystems. These collectives are not about including every possible actor, which could quickly become overwhelming; instead, they focus on pinpointing those individuals or groups with the highest capacity to trigger transformations within their sphere of influence.
- **Fixation effects should be prevented and avoided.** Fixation effects occur when participants become focused on a unique idea, solution, or thought process, which can limit creativity and prevent exploration of alternative, innovative approaches. These effects are

common in collaborative settings where preconceived notions, dominant voices, or early ideas influence the group’s thinking.

- **The workshops must be structured as to support a “resilient-fit” instead of a “quick-fit”.**

A ‘quick-fit’ approach focuses on rapid problem-solving, where solutions are designed to address immediate needs but may lack long-term viability or adaptability. In contrast, a ‘resilient-fit’ approach emphasizes solutions that are adaptable, durable, and capable of evolving over time to withstand changing circumstances and unforeseen challenges.

2.4. Phase 4 – Co-design outcomes **Essential Worksheet 4**

The fourth phase of co-design consists in formulating the outcomes of the co-design process., which may consist in a variety of services. Unlike a quick-fit approach that only addresses immediate outcomes, the resilient-fit approach ensures sustainable and adaptive service development by considering a broader range of use cases, collaboration modalities, and time horizons. The outcomes phase supports this approach by helping synthesize key findings from the co-design process, strengthening stakeholder engagement, providing a strategic roadmap across different time horizons, and facilitating continuous improvement. It ensures that services are resilient, user-centric, and aligned with long-term goals, allowing them to adapt and sustain within a complex ecosystem.

Beyond the provision of a specific service, co-design may result in different outcomes, such as:

- **Capacity building** - The co-design process enables the service developer to expand their expertise across a variety of fields. At the same time, users, like city stakeholders, gain familiarity with integrating data into their tools and practices and develop skills in collaborative work methods..
- **Research projects** – The co-design process helps identify potential research areas with other users, focusing on broad topics of interest. Additionally, it opens pathways for collaboration with other service providers within the stakeholders ecosystems, who can address specific user needs by contributing complementary expertise and technical solutions.
- **Opportunities for subsequent collaboration** - The co-design initiative can lead to a number of networking opportunities within professional communities, where the developed solutions and methodologies could be shared, potentially serving as models for adaptation in similar contexts elsewhere.

The materialization of these outcomes can unfold on various time horizons (short-term, mid-term, long-term). Therefore, it is essential to adopt a dynamic perspective that encourages the development of resilient and enduring relationships among the stakeholders involved in the co-design activities.

The toolkit tools to formalize and consider these outcomes under the form of a resilient action plan.

3. Detailed content of the co-design toolkit

The toolkit is organized into four distinct sections, each corresponding to one of the four phases of the co-design process (figure 5). Each worksheet is tailored to the specific needs and objectives of its respective phase, ensuring a structured approach to co-design. Within each worksheet, toolkit users will find a curated set of tools designed to facilitate the activities and goals of that phase. To enhance usability and efficiency, these tools come with ready-to-use template.

Figure 5. Overall structure of the toolkit

3.1. Tools for Phase 1: User Approach

Worksheet 1 – Approaching users and the user monitoring framework

The user monitoring framework focuses on establishing relationships with promising potential users, building and launching co-design activities with them. As such, eventually, this framework is intended to be used by service providers to engage in co-design activities with potential users during the initial stages of service design. This worksheet introduces the monitoring framework and how it can be used for approaching users.

Template 1.0.1 – Stakeholder ID Cards and assessment radars

ID cards and assessment radars should be used to gather information on stakeholders and projects within the potential use ecosystem and evaluate their relevance in relation to the target service. They help gather and structure information systematically, enabling cumulative learning and enriching the knowledge base. This template provides service providers with editable Excel files for stakeholder ID cards and an assessment radar to support their user approach process.

Template 1.0.2 - Project ID Cards and assessment radars

ID cards and assessment radars should be used to gather information on stakeholders and projects within the potential use ecosystem and evaluate their relevance in relation to the target service. They help gather and structure information systematically, enabling cumulative learning and enriching the knowledge base. This template provides service providers with editable Excel files for project ID cards and an assessment radar to support their user approach process.

Template 1.0.3 - Ecosystem mapping method [Coming soon]

The ecosystem mapping, based on the “ID Cards” and the “assessment radars”, gives a global overview of the potential usage ecosystem to understand the key challenge and opportunities it shows regarding the exploitation of data. This template provides service provider with an editable file to build their ecosystem map

3.2. Tools for the Phase 2: Diagnosis

Worksheet 2 – Co-design diagnosis and the Data-Information-Value Framework

The Data-Information-Value (D.I.V.) framework is a tool designed to assess potential services within the co-design process. It provides a methodological framework for analyzing data transformation processes from raw data to information usable in various contexts, and maps the stakeholders involved throughout this data-to-usage chain. It aims to highlight critical areas for improvement and opportunities for value-embedding EO applications. This worksheet introduces the D.I.V framework and how it should be used to perform co-design diagnosis.

Template 2.0.1 – Data-Information-Value Framework

This template is an editable Power Point file including the Data-Information-Value Framework. It should be used by service providers to perform their co-design diagnosis based on the Data-Information-Value framework

Worksheet 2.1 - Competency map

The competency map is a complementary worksheet associated with the Data-Information-Value framework. This tool provides a framework to assess the competencies needed, available, and/or that must be added to the project to facilitate the co-design activities.

3.3. Tools for the Phase 3: Workshops

Worksheet 3 – Guiding principles to build a co-design protocol

This worksheet provides service providers with some generic guidelines as well as advanced tips to structure a successful protocol to perform a co-design workshop, depending on the goal of the workshop, the attendees and the state of the relationship.

Worksheet 3.1 — Usefulness workshops

Workshops focused on investigating usefulness concentrate on identifying users' needs, usage profiles, usage scenarios, and constraints. This worksheet outlines the logic behind these workshops, how they should be organized, and also introduces templates and exercises to successfully conduct them.

Template 3.1.1 — Template for user profile

This template helps define and categorize the different user segments relevant to a specific theme. During a workshop, it helps identifying various user profiles based on their needs, roles, and potential interactions with the theme, ensuring a better understanding of target audiences and enabling the start of the development of a tailored solution.

Template 3.1.2 — Template for use scenario identification

This template helps identify and select potential promising use cases, then develop them into detailed scenarios. It outlines the steps, stakeholders, tools, and data involved in each scenario. Using visual aids like storyboards and diagrams, it provides a structured approach to exploring and refining how these use cases can be implemented in practical contexts.

Template 3.1.3 — Template for user needs expansion

This template helps refine and expand the results of templates 3.1.1 & 3.1.2 by using the insights gathered from these initial tools to build a more precise and comprehensive picture of the user profiles and usage scenarios. By integrating the detailed information from both canvases, it allows for a deeper understanding of the identified challenges and opportunities, ensuring that the solutions developed are more relevant and aligned with the broader ecosystem.

Template 3.1.4 — Template for integration challenges

This template is designed to explore how a proposed service could be integrated into users' existing practices, tools, and environments. It helps identify potential barriers and opportunities across skills, equipment, processes, and digital ecosystems. The outcome is a clear picture of what is already available today, what needs to evolve, and what support is required for successful adoption.

Worksheet 3.2 — Operability workshops

Workshops focused on operability issues concentrate on identifying the technical challenges related to the development and operation of the service. This worksheet outlines the rationale behind these workshops, how they should be organized, and also introduces templates and exercises to successfully carry them out.

Worksheet 3.3 — Usability workshops

The Usability Workshop is designed to evaluate how the developed services perform in practice when tested directly with end users and are integrated into their practices and tools. It ensures that prototypes are not only functional but also intuitive, efficient, and aligned with real users' workflows. This worksheet outlines the rationale behind these workshops, how they should be organized, and also introduces templates and exercises to successfully carry them out.

Template 3.3.1 — User feedback form

User Feedback Form is intended for participants. It guides them to reflect on clarity, usefulness, workflow integration, adoption barriers, and support needs. This form is suitable for usability workshops, as it offers a straightforward way for users to express their experience in their own words and to prioritise improvements.

Template 3.3.2 — Facilitator capture sheet

Facilitator Capture Sheet is intended for note-takers and facilitators. It provides a simple structure to record what happens in real time during exercises, particularly in usability workshops. By capturing strengths, challenges, and unexpected findings as they occur, it ensures that important insights are not lost and makes synthesis afterwards more efficient.

Worksheet 3.4 — The Data-Use-Need Matrix

This worksheet matches the users' needs identified during workshops with the available or required technological building blocks. It classifies commonalities across themes, assesses the availability of relevant technologies, and identifies where internal or external expertise is needed.

Template 3.4.1 — The Data-Use-Need Matrix

This template provides service providers with an editable file integrating a generic, blank version of the Data-Use-Need Matrix. It should be used by service providers to build their service design strategy based on the needs identified with users.

Worksheet 3.5 — Data Management Plan [Coming soon]

This worksheet introduces the Data Management Plan, which is a central tool to design reliable data-based services based on various types of data.

Template 3.5.1 — Data Management Plan [Coming soon]

This template provides service providers with an editable file integrating a generic, blank version of the Data Management Plan. It should be used by service providers to design reliable data-based services based on the needs identified with users.

3.4. Tools for the Phase 4: Outcomes

Worksheet 4 — The outcomes diagram

The outcomes diagram is a tool used to help the stakeholders involved in the co-design process to synthesize the outcomes of their joint actions. Its goal is to support the formulation of valuable outcomes and actions plans beyond the services by integration other kinds of collaboration such as research projects for instance. It is a key element of resilient-fit co-design. This worksheet introduces the outcomes diagram and how it should be use throughout the co-design process.

Template 4.0.1 — The outcomes diagram

This template provides service providers with an editable file integrating a generic, blank outcomes diagram. It should be used by service providers in the phase 4 of the co-design process to formalize the outcomes of the co-design process and the potential follow up with users and partners.

Worksheet 4.1 — The sustainability canvas

The Sustainability Canvas is a practical co-design tool designed to help service providers ensure that DestinE-based services are not only innovative, but also technically robust, economically viable, and strategically durable. By articulating six interdependent dimensions—

unique value proposition, user value, user relationship, technical solution, workflow and working model, and economic equation—the canvas provides a structured framework for examining what makes a service sustainable in the long term.

Template 4.1.1 — The sustainability canvas

This template provides service providers with an editable file integrating a generic, blank version of the sustainability canvas. It should be used by service providers to build a sustainable model for service operation and strategic development.

Worksheet 4.2 — Fostering retrofit towards genericity [Coming soon]

This worksheet introduces the concept of retrofit, a design strategy which relies on building services based on generic technology building blocks that can be integrated within the DestinE Platform and be re-used in subsequent co-design project. It enlightens some key mechanisms that can be enacted all along the co-design process to foster retrofit.

Worksheet 5 — The illustrative case of Marseille [Coming soon]

This worksheet illustrates an entire co-design journey through the case of a service co-design with the municipality of Marseille. In this case, the four phases of the co-design process are illustrated and concrete examples are provided on how the tools and methods introduced in the toolkit were used.

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APPENDIX

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Background: Some landmark in the history of the co-design methods

The development of co-design methods can rely on major efforts by the academic community in design sciences, innovation, and management sciences. In this section, we propose a brief overview of the chronological evolution of the co-design methods, based on the academic literature.

Co-design in the design and innovation management literatures²

1970s-1990s: Co-design of embedded systems

The term “co-design” appeared first in the 70s to designate the design of “embedded computer systems”, i.e. software that operate in complex systems. According to (De Micheli and Gupta 1997), “hardware/software co-design means meeting system-level objectives by exploiting the synergism of hardware and software through their concurrent design.” (p. 349).

As underlined by (Dubois 2015) in his in-depth analysis of co-design history, there is a “myth” in this early representation of co-design, just as there is a myth in co-design today. Dubois cites De Micheli and Gupta: “co-design can lead to products of superior quality (i.e., performance/cost, flexibility) with a shorter design and development time as compared to traditional integrated circuit design methodologies” And this type of co-design was mainly oriented towards technical software techniques (CAD, integrated simulation software, etc.). Despite limited success and adoption, this first wave of co-design works underlines several issues related to co-design situations:

- Higher integration between heterogenous types of expertise throughout the development process so that design work cannot be divided in a linear or modular way.
- Integrated learning: the authors underline the necessity of “co-simulation” (Wolf 1994). “Co-simulation usually refers to some sort of mixed hardware-software simulation-for example, one part of the system may be modeled as instructions executing on a CPU while another part may be modeled as logic gates.” (p. 980). More generally this underlines the necessity to organize learning at the crossroad of different types of expertise.
- Co-design situations, at least at this time, could be driven by a shared list of requirements: “Whereas performance is the most important design criterion for information processing systems, reliability, availability, and safety are extremely important for control systems” (De Micheli and Gupta 1997).

1990s-2000s: co-design as a relationship between buyers and suppliers

In the end of the 1990s, another stream of work analyzes the relationship between buyers and suppliers. Integrators and suppliers are not only contracting and bargaining on price and logistics conditions but are actually “co-designing” more and more. In automotive industry, it is said that Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) and first tier suppliers “co-design” to actually designate situations where OEMs delegate the design of components, modules or systems to their suppliers.

² This part has been extracted from the deliverable WP2-D2.6 of the e-shape project, produced by Raphaëlle Barbier

These co-design situations lead to shed light on new critical features:

- Scholars underline the relationship issues: how to contract? How to make sure that the supplier has the required design competences, and also the required co-design competences, meaning the capacity to collaborate in design phases? (Araz and Ozkarahan 2007).
- The co-design goal is usually relatively well-identified by the list of requirements that define the object/service to be developed.
- Interestingly enough, this form of co-design could appear as a form of “dis-integration” of the design of a complex system (by opposition of the co-design of embedded systems). It underlines the fact that co-design is not necessarily an increased integration but, more than that, is the capacity to organize coordination and division of design work that is adapted to the most complex systems.
- The participants have very heterogenous knowledge and competences (lay user vs professional designers or scientists can participate in co-design workshops).
- The collective logic is extremely loose, compared to the buyer/supplier co-design mentioned above (very limited contractual aspects).

In the 2000s: co-design as user involvement

In the end of the 2000s, co-design is also used to account for designing with users. Scholars in innovation management and design describe planned meetings in which professional designers organize user involvement in the design of new products and services (Le Masson and Magnusson 2005; Magnusson 2003; Sanders 2002; Sanders and Stappers 2008). As explained in (Dubois 2015), the processes rely on tools and techniques such as mental maps, drawings, prototyping, storyboarding, product and use lifecycle. Good practices are described into details in (Sanders and Dandavate 1999; Brandt et al. 2004). And in a review, (Mattelmäki et al. 2011) underlines that the term ‘co-design’ is quite ambiguous but encompasses the following dimensions of the user-involvement based co-design methods:

- Co-design is “utilized in design context in which designers are involved, and the topic of the activity is related to design exploration, envisioning and solution development”.
- Co-design has “an empowering mindset and it gives voice and tools to those who were not traditionally part of design process”.
- Co-design is “about engagement of potential users but also about stakeholder collaboration”.
- Co-design includes “process and tools of collaborative engagement, events for learning and exploration”.

Co-design for downstream earth observation services

Before 2019 and the e-shape project

In order to connect distant data and usages ecosystems, several approaches have been promoted and implemented by the Earth Observation (EO) community in the last decades. The first one consists in having each ecosystem bridging independently half the distance, through an ‘open-data’ strategy (Borzacchiello and Craglia, 2012; Zotti and Mantia, 2014): on the one hand, data is made available in open access with open standards; on the other hand, the different stakeholders take advantage of these resources by integrating them in their own usage context. Despite being necessary to broaden the usages of data, this approach has proved to be insufficient in practice, as the stakeholders tend to have difficulty making use of EO data spontaneously.

This accounts for the complementary efforts of the climate-modelling community to operate a second approach that consists in connecting the distant ecosystems of data and usages by encouraging the development of operational services based on climate data, through specific ‘co-design’ activities. An important stream of literature documents the implementation of such an approach in the case of climate services. This stream of literature is relevant to our

application case as climate-modelling integrates heterogeneous data sources such as in situ data and earth observations.

In this context, co-design (also referred as ‘co-production’ or ‘co-development’ depending on the authors) mostly relates to the involvement of data users in order to adjust user demands and the supply of useful information (McNie, 2012). Without appropriate processes, this might lead to ad hoc small-scale and short-lived data-based services. However, although co-design tends to be increasingly used, the EO community also underlines that it would deserve further formalisation beyond the buzzword (Goodess et al., 2019)

The critical contribution of e-shape (2019-2023): the resilient-fit co-design

An innovative co-design methodology was developed by Mines Paris PSL within the EU-funded Horizon 2020 e-shape project (standing for “EuroGEO Showcases: Application Powered by Europe”). By its scale and number of partners (EUR 15 million; 54 partners), e-shape was a unique initiative bringing together decades of public investment and expert teams, into operational services with high socio-economic value for citizens, the industry, the decision-makers and the researchers.

An innovative co-design methodology was developed within e-shape. Over a four-year period, e-shape delivered 37 Pilot Services in seven independent thematic areas³ seeking to deliver concrete societal benefits from the use of Copernicus data combined with the use of the DIAS cloud-computing platforms. The co-design methodology was therefore specifically developed to address the gap between data science (i.e. Earth Observation, cloud computing) and usages (i.e. delivering on policy priorities and generating citizen benefits), and delivered a co-design taxonomy, and associated processes, along several co-design Types.

Barbier et al. (2023) have modelled and successfully advanced new forms of co-design (so-called resilient-fit co-design) between EO data providers and unknown users. The methodology was built from the generalization of a large panel of diverse and complex “real-world” use cases, which triggered a virtuous feedback process and improvements of the methodology itself from a large panel of end-user interactions. The rooting of the conceptual framework into actual use cases ensured the usability and relevance of the methodology, which has made its overall success.

The method involved a diagnosis phase (performed on 37 pilot), and a workshop phase (preparatory step, design sessions and debriefing). It proposed 4 types of co-design corresponding to the need of (re)building adequate relationships with a specific class of actors and to identify the level of the unknown in the problem space (here related to the nature of data usages) and in the solution space (here related to the nature of the data-based solution addressing identified problem).

The toolkit and methods presented in this document represent not only an adaptation of these contributions to the specific context of Destination Earth but also include newly developed approaches tailored to address its unique challenges, fostering genericity alongside contextualization.

³ Agriculture, health, energy, ecosystem, water, disasters, climate.

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The Center of Management Science of Mines Paris is a pioneering laboratory in management sciences since 1967. Its research strategy is based on three axes: 1) design activities and innovation capacities in global enterprises and production systems; 2) dynamics of trades and occupational health in innovation and service activities; 3) Institutional changes and new forms of governance (private and public) in a capitalism of innovation and sustainable development.

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